

A Study on Consumer Satisfaction Towards Maruti Suzuki in Thoothukudi

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Abstract

The Indian passenger-car industry has been on the continuous growth due to healthy progress of economy and development of road facilities supported by easy vehicle financing for prospective buyers. The user prefers this because of its accessibility; adaptability to individual wants door to door services and reliability. Using motor car for transportation is comfortable and save enormous energy and time. The study has been conducted to know the consumer satisfaction towards Maruti Suzuki cars. These car is a very vital transport style to travel from one place to another place.

Keywords: Economy, Service and Reliability, Maruti Suzuki Cars.

Introduction

Maruti Suzuki India limited, formerly known as Maruti udyog limited, a subsidiary of Suzuki Motor Corporation of japan, is India largest passenger car company. Maruti Suzuki has been the leader of the Indian car market for over two and a half decades. The company has two manufacturing facilities located at Gurgaon and Haryana. It is the largest car manufacturing company in India. Maruti Suzuki is one of the India’s leading automobile manufactures and the market in the car segment. It was the first company in India to mass-produce and sell more than a million cars. The company offered different range of cars from passenger cars to sports cars. The company offers 15 brands popular cars such as the Swift, Celerio, Swift Dzire, Wagan R, Ertiga, Ciaz, Baleno and Baleno RS, Alto.

People who seek the assistance of producers for satisfying their needs are known as consumers. Today business around the world recognizes “Consumers is King” knowing why and how people consume. In business world, all the goods are produced for consumers. Without consumers one can’t lead in his business. Customer satisfaction depends on the product’s perceived performance relative to the buyer’s expectations. If the product’s performance falls short

of expectations, the customer is dissatisfied. If performance matches expectations, the customer is satisfied. If performance exceeds expectations, the customer is highly satisfied or delighted. Because customers buy satisfaction, not just parts, marketing managers must be constantly concerned with product quality. Quality means a product's ability to satisfy a customer's needs or requirements. Quality and satisfaction depend on the total product offering.

Review of literature

ArpitaSrivastava (2014) a study entitled that "The Consumer Behavior towards Passengers Cars with reference to Delhi in Tamil Nadu", Consumer Behavior consists of all human behavior that goes in making purchase decisions. An understanding of the consumer behavior enables a marketer to take marketing decisions which are compatible with its consumer needs. There are four major classes of consumer behavior determinants and expectations, namely, cultural, socio-economic, personal and psychological.

Suganya R, (2012) in her research paper highlights the effect of brand equity on consumer purchasing behavior on car. The paper speaks that brand plays vital role in car sales, not only to attract but also to retain customers. The author concluded that brand awareness and perceived quality proved to influence the brand loyalty. Also brand loyalty and brand association affect customers' attitudes towards brand.

Ganesan.G, (2007) A study entitled "Branding – A stable and sustainable Asset" - A study observed that branding create positive emotional association in our market for our product or service is important. It can create want and desire by the mere mention of our brand, product or service name. Needless do says that's powerful. Such positive emotional associations are built over time through good branding practice and a time tested relationship between our business and our customer based on intrigue, trust understanding and support.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the factors influencing the purchase of Maruti Suzuki car.
- To known the customer level of satisfaction.

Scope of the Study

The scope of study is limited to the respondents are selected from in and around Thoothukudi.

Methodology

The study is based on survey method. For this study both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data were collected from the respondents who were selected by applying convenient sampling technique. The data were collected from 80 respondents who reside in and around Thoothukudi. Secondary data was collected from published books, journals, magazines, websites, and newspapers and so on.

General Profile

Profiles of the Respondent

1	Gender	No of Respondent	Percentage
	Male	63	78.75
	Female	17	21.25
	Total	80	100

2	Age		
	Below 25	5	6.25
	26 to 35years	11	13.75
	36 to 45years	38	47.5
	Above 45 years	26	32.5
	Total	80	100.0
3	Occupation		
	Business	20	25
	Private employee	23	28.75
	Professional	16	20
	Government employee	12	15
	Others	9	11.25
	Total	80	100.0
4	Monthly Income		
	Up to Rs.20,000	24	30
	Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000	36	45
	Rs.30,001 to Rs.40000	14	17.5
	Above Rs.40,000	6	7.5
	Total	80	100
5	Type of Maruti Suzuki Cars		
	Sedan	31	38.75
	Muv	13	16.25
	Suv	20	25
	Luxury	16	20
	Total	80	100

From the table portrait that 78.75 percent of respondent are male have a rest of them are female. The table inferred that more than 47.5 percent of the age group of respondent that 36- 45. The table shows that 28.75 percent high of the private employee. Table shows that high as 45 percent of monthly income level in Rs. 20,001 to Rs. 30,000. Then the table portrait that 38.75 percent of the respondent used for sedan car

Table 6 Factors Considered for Purchasing of Car

Factors consider	No of Respondents	Percentage
Millage	28	35
Price	21	26.25
Safety	17	21.25
Comfort	11	13.75
Finance	3	3.75
Total	80	100

It is inferred that 35 percent of the respondents prefer millage, 26.25 percent of the respondents

prefer price, 21.25 percent of the respondents prefer safety, 13.75 percent of the respondents prefer comfort and 3.75 percent of the respondents prefer finance. Thus majority of the respondents (35 percent) prefer Millage.

Table 7 Null Hypothesis (H0)

There is no significant difference between the occupation of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regards to customer satisfaction towards Maruti Suzuki.

Occupation and Satisfaction Level of Maruti Suzuki

Occupation	Level of Satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Business	5	12	3	20
Private employee	3	8	12	23
Professional	6	6	4	16
Govt employee	3	7	2	12
Others	1	5	3	9
Total	18	38	24	80

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	Df	Sig.value
Chi-Square	14.35	8	15.57*

Significances 5%

The calculated value is less than the value at 5 % level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings

- Majority of males respondent used in the Maruti Suzuki Car.
- The study also inferred that more than 47.5 percent of the age group of respondent that 36- 45.
- The study shows that 28.75 percent high of the private employee.
- The monthly income (45 percent) of the respondents earns an up to Rs. 20,001 to Rs. 30,000.
- The type of maruti car portrait that 38.75 percent of the sedan car used.
- There is no significant difference between the occupation of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regards to customer satisfaction towards maruti Suzuki.

Conclusion

Consumer behavior consists of all human behavior that goes in making purchase decisions. An understanding of the consumer behavior enables a marketer to take marketing decisions which are compatible with its consumer needs. There are four major classes of consumer behavior determinants and expectations, namely, cultural, socio-economic, personal and psychological. Rising income has enhanced the purchasing power and more and more people are able to afford a car. All these activities are aimed to increase the customer loyalty and thus retaining customers.

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